

Table 1. Foliage and grain yield from CN705-18. Chinsurah, India, 1988.

Parameter	Control (no cut)	1 cut	2 cuts
Foliage yield (t/ha)			
1st cut	—	3.8	3.6
2d cut	—	—	3.4
At harvest	2.1	1.9	2.0
Total	2.1	5.7	9.0
Grain yield (t/ha)	1.0	1.1	1.4
Days to 50% flowering	171	175	167

similar. Yields in the double cut crop were higher. Flowering was early in the double cut crop, followed by the normal crop and by the single cut crop.

Number of effective tillers at harvest was significantly higher in the double cut crop and 1,000-grain weight

Table 2. Effect of leaf cutting on yield components. Chinsurah, India.

Character	Treatment			Percent increase or decrease over control
	No cut	1 cut	2 cuts	
Plant ht (cm)	205.0	200.0	182.0	- 11
Effective tillers at harvest (no.)	6.0	10.0	12.0	+100
Panicle length (cm)	23.4	22.0	22.5	- 4
Total grains per panicle	202.0	185.0	156.0	- 23
1000-grain wt	24.1	24.3	25.4	+ 5
Percent of sterile grains/panicle	1.9	3.6	4.2	-
Yield per plant (gm)	28.0	41.0	45.0	+ 61
Grain-to-straw ratio	0.5	0.5	0.7	-

increased slightly. Grain yield/plant and grain-to-straw ratio also increased. Plant height, total grains/panicle, and length of panicle were reduced (Table 2).

The increased number of effective tillers contributed 61% of the yield increase. The shorter plant height

contributed to better grain filling.

This preliminary study shows that herbage production is possible with photoperiod-sensitive deepwater rice, without sacrificing grain yield. □

Improving rice yield using hydrocortisone spray

K. Manian, R. Govindarasu, P. Sivasubramanian, and N. Natarajaratnam, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru College of Agriculture, Karaikal 609605, Union Territory of Pondicherry, India

The effect of hydrocortisone, a glucocorticoid hormone of higher animals, has been found to be beneficial for germination of rice. We assessed the effect of hydrocortisone on dry matter production, grain yield, and harvest index.

Hydrocortisone (50 ppm) was sprayed at different growth stages—active tillering phase (50 d after sowing [DAS]), flowering (75 DAS), and grain filling (100 DAS)—of a standing crop of IR20 at Karaikal. Spraying at flowering significantly improved grain yield and increased dry matter production (see table). Dry matter production increased most with spray at active tillering phase, but yield increased only 12%.

This trend suggests that dry matter production is stimulated by hydrocortisone spray during tillering phase, but its use for increasing grain productivity is limited. Similarly, spraying at grain filling phase did not

Effect of spraying hydrocortisone at different growth stages on yield, dry matter production, and harvest index per plot basis (16 m²).^a Pondicherry, India.

	Control	Active tillering (50 DAS)	Flowering (75 DAS)	Grain filling (100 DAS)	LSD (5%)
Yield (g)	9.10	10.21 (12)	11.00 (21)	10.30 (13)	1.16
Dry matter production (g)	21.81	26.38 (21)	25.58 (17)	24.70 (13)	4.04
Harvest index	0.41	0.39 (-6)	0.43 (4)	0.41 (-2)	ns

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase over control.

improve grain yield or dry matter production. To improve dry matter production and grain yield

simultaneously, a spray or hydrocortisone of 50 ppm at flowering stage is optimum. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Using a chlorophyll meter to predict need for topdressed nitrogen

F. T. Turner and M. F. Jund, Texas A&M Agriculture Research and Extension Center, Route 7 Box 999, Beaumont, Texas 77713, USA

Preliminary results show that a hand-held chlorophyll meter comes closer

than any other technique as a simple, quick, and accurate method for predicting the need to topdress N in semidwarf rice. A relationship between the chlorophyll content of the newest expanded leaf and the need for N fertilizer has been developed in 2 yr of experiments in research plots at Beaumont and in 1 yr at Bay City and Eagle Lake, Texas (see table).

We tested semidwarf Lemont variety